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A Study on the SME Entrepreneurs Level of Satisfaction in Business for Efficient and Entrepreneurship - On the Basis of Field Survey

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Abstract

Anyone who manages a business and earns income is an Entrepreneur. First, it is considered important to know about them and their level of satisfaction in their profession. Also, only if they are satisfied with the business they will continue to do the business and many entrepreneurs will be formed. So, this study is developed with this aim in mind. Equally main and minor data are used in favor of this survey. Paper is empirical in nature as such data were collected with the help of websites. The sample size is 500. The study emphasized the collection of data from one city, Chennai. In it, questions related to challenges and expectations and some questions about the problems among entrepreneurs were asked. With this, it was revealed that there are a lot of expectations. Questions like challenge, expectation, needs, support, cash availability, customer attraction and overall satisfaction and travel were asked about business development. The only answer that all entrepreneurs have is to improve. That is what we are moving towards. If all the factors cooperate with us, we can definitely improve. We are currently growing. If we develop, the country will develop. This review reveals that "we have reached the level of satisfaction, although we are not fully satisfied due to several reasons."

Keywords: Satisfaction, Overall Perception, Mindset, SME Entrepreneurs, withstand, Value, Attitude, Decision making.

Introduction

When is a single man satisfied? He is fully satisfied only when he attains an understanding of himself and all the factors around him that depend on him. Similarly, when an individual becomes an entrepreneur, do we have all the qualifications to do business? Can we reach the goal? Can we face problems? Do we have enough academic knowledge of the industry? What is our vision for the profession? What is our mindset about starting a business? An entrepreneur can be satisfied if he has an understanding of these common questions. Because the understanding of the business knowledge is very important for an entrepreneur. Therefore, the internal objective of this study was to find out.

Main Aspiration of the Learn:

1. To determine satisfaction level of demographic profile..
2. To hit upon the perception of Entrepreneurs Mindset.
3. To find overall perception satisfaction of SME Entrepreneurs

Methodology & Statistical Tools

1. Direct investigation (Field survey).
2. Area of the study is Chennai.
3. Both Primary & Secondary data used.
4. Random Sampling Technique.
5. Sample size 500.
6. Chi-square analysis & simple percentage with simple ranking method of tools were used.

Literature Review

1. **OT JOEL, VU OGUANOBI (2024)** these perceptual studies are important because of the entrepreneurial leadership and growths explain past, future, present and long term success also. Here explain characteristics, decision making and principles.
2. **Thaimuta, J., Ngugi, P., & Nyang'au, S. (2024)**. Idea of the learn in the direction of that industrial inspiration capability in SMEs. Area of the study is Nairobi country in Kenya. Also explain internal and external operations regarding lack of entrepreneurial skills

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1. Observation and result shown in below table showing satisfaction level of socio - demographic profile

Overall information	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Total
Company Registration	9	31	21	7	68
Gender	33	34	12	3	82
Age	26	20	5	1	52
Education	19	15	20	3	57
Family background	11	14	22	4	51
Experience	18	43	14	6	81
Special Licensing	10	37	13	2	62
Turnover	13	19	10	5	47
Total	139	213	117	31	500

Primary source

H₀: There is no close relationship between the satisfaction level of all the personal information and the achievement achieved by the respondents agreed opinion.

H₁: There is very close relationship between the satisfaction level of all the personal information and the achievement achieved by the respondents agreed opinion.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Degree of liberty} &= (\text{Column} - 1) \times (\text{Row} - 1), \\ &= 4-1 \times 8-1 = 3 \times 7 \quad \text{D.F.} = 21 \end{aligned}$$

Chi Square Test

factor	Designed X ² Value	Board value	D.F. at 5% level	Remarks
Purpose	64.83	32.67	21	Significant

Conclusion: Since, the calculated value of X² is greater than the table value of X², H₀ is rejected. Consequently, bring to a close that present is very

close relationship between the satisfaction level of all the personal information and the achievement achieved by the respondents agreed opinion.

Chart-1 showing satisfaction level of socio -demographic profile

2. Perception of Entrepreneurs Mindset in the survey:

Next, what is the satisfaction level of their dispositional understanding? In the study, the response of all entrepreneurs was very positive. He patiently answered all the questions asked in the examination without any hesitation and answered them responsibly. Because, through the study, everyone gave very cooperative responses in the

mindset that something good would happen to the entrepreneurs. Thus, their responses were to the point where more research is needed. And the following questions were asked in this regard, among them, questions were asked in terms of attitude, ability, characteristics, educational training and view of SME of the entrepreneurs, and thus their satisfaction level was discussed and research was carried out with them.

2. Table showing perception of entrepreneur's mindset scoring with simple percentage and rank

Entrepreneurial Values, Attitudes and Decision making	Score	Percentage (100%)	Total Percentage Score	Rank
Entrepreneurial Values				
Innovativeness	45	9%		
Independence	65	13%		
Outstanding performance	42	8.4%		
Respect of Work	50	10%	40.4%	I
Entrepreneurial Attitudes				
Tendency to take moderate risk	23	4.6%		
Imagination	27	5.4%		
Eye for opportunities	19	3.8%		
Initiative	21	4.2%		
Self belief	31	6.2%		
Preference for feedback	20	4%	28.2%	III
Entrepreneurial Decision making				
Experience	48	9.6%		
Advice	35	7%		
Research	34	6.8%		
Heuristics	40	8%	31.4%	II
Total	500	100%	100%	

3. Table showing overall perception satisfaction Scoring with simple percentage and rank

Overall perception	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dis satisfied	Total
Entrepreneurial Mindset	38	34	25	12	109
Percentage	7.6	6.8	5	2.4	21.8
Entrepreneurial Skill	40	41	30	2	113
Percentage	8	8.2	6	0.4	22.6
Entrepreneur Characteristics	35	31	23	4	93
Percentage	7	6.2	4.6	0.8	18.6
Education Training	31	35	22	6	94
Percentage	6.2	7	4.4	1.2	18.8
Vision Of SME	36	30	20	5	91
Percentage	7.2	6	4	1	18.2
Overall Total	180	171	120	29	500
Overall Percentage Total	36%	34.2%	24%	5.8%	100%
Overall Rank	I	II	III	IV	

Chart-2 showing overall perception satisfaction

Conclusion

According to the saying "if you try you can achieve" all the entrepreneurs are working with some kind of initiative. Their persistence is appreciated here. Patience sustains their profession. There is no doubt that if there is a slight change in the mentality

of all the entrepreneurs and some changes in the administrative functions, surely they will all achieve success and move our country on the path of progress. Therefore, the conclusion of this study is that by encouraging them to focus more on the awareness of vocational education and full involvement in the

development program in the minds of all entrepreneurs, a good change can be seen in the SME sector. The most important objective of this study is that everyone should choose and create their own work. Unemployment and poverty should be eradicated. It is said that everyone, from the educated to the layman, with self-knowledge and self-satisfaction, will definitely achieve the ideal, fulfill the purpose and lead to success.

Let's move on! Let's make progress! Let's try first!

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